

Search for Intramolecular H-bonding in Thiophenols through UV Spectra

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The ultraviolet absorption spectra of *o*- and *p*-nitrothiophenols, *o*- and *p*-methylsulphonylthiophenols, and *o*- and *p*-chlorothiophenols in *n*-hexane or cyclohexane and in ethanol have been recorded and compared with those of the corresponding methyl ethers. The effect of methylation on the absorption spectrum of *o*-nitrothiophenol does not indicate intramolecular H-bonding. From the solvent effect it may be concluded that there is no or only very weak H-bonding in *o*-nitrothiophenol. The possibility of certain geometrical requirements to satisfy intramolecular H-bonding has been examined. *o*-Methylsulphonylthiophenol appears to have a more favourable configuration for internal H-bond formation than *o*-nitrothiophenol. The spectral data indicate the existence of weak intramolecular H-bonding in *o*-methylsulphonylthiophenol. No significant intramolecular H-bonding seems to exist in *o*-chlorothiophenol.

A number of investigations¹⁻⁶ have shown that SH group is capable of forming H-bonds, although the bonds are reported to be weak in many cases. Some workers⁷⁻¹¹ have, however, reported negative evidence for H-bond formation involving SH. This dichotomy in experimental findings prompted us to examine by means of uv spectra whether some thiophenols, suitably *ortho*-substituted, can form intramolecular H-bonding or not.

Experimental

o- and *p*-Chlorophenols were purified before use, b.p. 175–76° and 217° (m.p. 43°), respectively. *o*- and *p*-Chloroanisoles (b.p. 195–96° and 198°) were obtained by methylating the above phenols. *o*-Chlorothiophenol (b.p. 204–06°) was obtained as described in the literature¹². *p*-Chlorothiophenol (m.p. 54–5°) was obtained by the reduction of *p*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl chloride¹³ with zinc and sulphuric acid. *o*-Chlorophenyl methyl sulphide (b.p. 118°/16 mm) and *p*-chlorophenyl methyl sulphide (b.p. 224°) were obtained by the methylation of the respective thiophenols. *o*-Nitrothiophenol (m.p. 57–8°) was prepared by the reduction of di-*o*-nitrophenyl disulphide¹⁴. *p*-Nitrothiophenol (m.p. 75°) was prepared by the reported method¹⁵. Methyl *o*-nitrophenyl sulphide (m.p. 59–60°) and methyl *p*-nitrophenyl sulphide (m.p. 72°) were obtained by methylating the corresponding thiophenols with methyl iodide in alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution.

o-Methylsulphonylthiophenol : The compound was prepared by converting *o*-methylthionitrobenzene to *o*-methylsulphonylnitrobenzene which in turn was converted to *o*-methylsulphonylaniline and finally to *o*-methylsulphonylthiophenol.

o-Methylthionitrobenzene was oxidised with potassium permanganate solution in glacial acetic acid to yield the sulphone, m.p. 105°. It was reduced¹⁶ with ferrous sulphate to *o*-methylsulphonylaniline, m.p. 82°. The aniline (7 g) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (10 ml) and water (90 ml) and diazotised with sodium nitrite (2.8 g in 15 ml of water). The diazonium chloride solution was treated with a solution of potassium ethyl xanthate (25 g in 30 ml of water). The xanthogenic ester was hydrolysed using KOH (5 g) pellets. Since the thiophenol was not steam-volatile, it was ether-extracted and the extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the product was distilled, (1.5 g), b.p. 159°/5 mm (Found : C, 44.3 ; H, 4.1. C₇H₈O₂S₂ calcd. for : C, 44.7 ; H, 4.3%).

o-Methylsulphonylphenyl methyl sulphide : The foregoing compound, after methylating in the usual way, yielded the sulphide which was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 81–2° (Found : C, 47.3 ; H, 4.9. C₈H₁₀O₂S₂ calcd. for : C, 47.5 ; H, 5.0%).

p-Methylsulphonylthiophenol : It was prepared from *p*-methylsulphonylaniline by the same procedure as used for the *ortho*-isomer. Though the compound was reported by Burton and Hu¹⁷, its physical constant was not given. The thiophenol boiled at 132°/22 mm (Found : C, 44.4 ; H, 4.0. C₇H₈O₂S calcd. for : C, 44.7, H, 4.3%).

p-Methylsulphonylphenyl methyl sulphide : It was prepared by methylating the above thiophenol, m.p. 98° (lit.¹⁷ 98–9°).

Spectral measurements : The spectra were taken in hexane or cyclohexane and in ethanol (95%) on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

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Results and Discussion

In the present investigation the compounds examined for intramolecular H-bonding are *o*-nitrothiophenol, *o*-methylsulphonylthiophenol and *o*-chlorothiophenol.

The detection of H-bond formation by means of uv spectra depends upon studying the effect of solvent on absorption. Phenols, in the absence of internal H-bonding in them and intramolecular steric effects in their methyl ethers, absorb in a nonpolar solvent like hexane at shorter wavelengths but in ethanol at longer wavelengths than the corresponding methyl ethers^{18,19}. In a chelated

phenol (1) the polarity of the absorbing system is increased by polarisation. Methylation of such a phenol reduces the polarity of the absorbing system and causes a hypsochromic shift. The effect of solvent on the uv spectra of chelated phenols and nonchelated phenols can be seen from the data given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SOLVENT EFFECT ON UV SPECTRA OF CHELATED AND NON-CHELATED PHENOLS*

Phenol	Hexane		Ethanol	
	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$
Salicylaldehyde	328.5	9200	325	3000
	265	10000	255	10000
Me ether of salicylaldehyde	310	5600	319.5	4200
	246.5	12000	253	11700
<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	308	4900	316	2900
	247	15800	254	8500
Me ether of <i>m</i> -hydroxybenzaldehyde	309	2900	314.5	2800
	249	8500	252.5	8300
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenone	329	4300	327	3150
	255	10500	251.5	9300
Me ether of <i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone	300	3800	305	3800
	242.5	7950	246	11500
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	346	3900	343.5	3600
	271	7600	273	6600
Me ether of <i>o</i> -nitrophenol	259	3450	317	2850
	287 ^a	10400	314	18000

*Data for Sl. nos. 1–6 are from Ref. 18, for Sl. nos 7 and 8 from Ref. 20, for Sl. no. 9 from Ref. 21.

^aSolvent cyclohexane.

The spectral behaviour of *o*-nitrothiophenol and its methyl ether both in *n*-hexane and ethanol is given in Table 2; for comparison, the spectral data of *p*-nitrothiophenol and its methyl ether are also given. *o*-Nitrothiophenol and its methyl ether show a *B*-band at about 350 nm and a *K*-band ($\epsilon > 10000$) at about 240 nm. *p*-Nitrothiophenol and its methyl ether do not show the *B*-band; they exhibit the

K-band in the 300–340 nm region. The appearance of the *B*-band for *ortho*-substituted compounds in the long wavelength region is a general phenomenon (Table 1). The appearance of *B*-bands in *ortho*-substituted compounds and their non-appearance in the *para*-isomers seem to throw light on the nature of the electronic transition responsible for *B*-bands. According to Burawoy²², *B*-bands originate from the electronic migrations along the conjugated system formed by the three benzene double bonds as indicated in 2 for methyl *o*-nitrophenyl sulphide. Substituents *ortho* to double bond groups are terminal groups of the absorbing system and responsible for appreciable red-shifts, whereas in the *para*-position they are in a side-chain and have much smaller effects. Moreover, since the transition moment is smaller, the lower intensities of the *B*-bands compared with those of the *K*-bands become understandable.

TABLE 2—UV SPECTRA OF *o*-NITROTHIOPHENOL, METHYL *o*-NITROPHENYL SULPHIDE AND THEIR *p*-ISOMERS

Compd.	Hexane		Ethanol	
	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$
<i>o</i> -Nitrothiophenol	345	3300	349	2900
	238	15600	239	11000
Methyl <i>o</i> -nitrophenyl-sulphide	362	3700	379	3400
	243	20100	244	18000
<i>p</i> -Nitrothiophenol	304	11800	324	7700
Methyl <i>p</i> -nitrophenyl-sulphide	325	15900	341	13100

The *B*- and *K*-bands of phenols, in which there is no intramolecular H-bonding, are displaced to longer wavelengths as the dielectric constant of the solvent increases²⁰. In the case of *p*-nitrothiophenol, a change from hexane to ethanol has displaced the *K*-band by 20 nm. This effect is mainly due to the increasing polarity of the absorbing system resulting partly from the dielectric constant of the solvent and partly from the formation of a true external H-bond in ethanol. On the other hand, the displacement for the *B*- and *K*-bands is 4 and 1 nm, respectively, for *o*-nitrothiophenol. This seems to suggest that there is no significant intramolecular H-bonding in *o*-nitrothiophenol. For phenols with a strong intramolecular H-bond, the shift is always hypsochromic for the *B*-band on changing the solvent from a nonpolar to a polar one; for the *K*-band no shift or a slight hypsochromic or bathochromic shift occurs (Table 1).

Methylation of *p*-nitrothiophenol causes a red-shift of 21 nm of the *K*-band with increase in intensity. This is the normal effect of methylation consistent with the greater electron-repelling power of the methyl group. Methylation of *o*-nitrothiophenol also results in a bathochromic shift of both the bands. In the case of intramolecularly H-bonded phenols, methylation displaces both the bands to shorter wavelengths (Table 1). This is due to a reversal of the bathochromic effect of the internal H-bond^{18,20}. Thus the effect of methylation on

the spectrum of *o*-nitrothiophenol does not indicate internal H-bond. Keeping the solvent effect in view, we may conclude that either there is no intramolecular H-bonding in *o*-nitrothiophenol or if it exists, it must only be very weak.

The feeble power of sulphur to be H-bonded with oxygen may be attributed to its lower electronegativity. Through this is an important factor in S-H...O bond formation, the apparent non-existence of even weak chelation in *o*-nitrothiophenol appears to be partly due to the geometry of the H-bond.

The studies conducted on the crystal structures of oxalic acid²³ and *p*-alkoxybenzoic and -cinnamic acids²⁴ revealed that the O-H...O bonds are rectilinear. The typical O-H...O hydrogen bond length²⁵ is 2.61–2.76 Å. If we draw a scale model of the structure of *o*-nitrophenol (3) representing the O-H...O bond as rectilinear, we find that the length of the H-bond is 2.5 Å and CÔH is 88° both of which are normal. Thus the geometry of the molecule is ideally suited for H-bond formation. On the other hand, when a similar structure is drawn for *o*-nitrothiophenol (4) we notice that the S-H...O distance is 2.6 Å and CŜH is 78°.

The bond length is normal. The angle 78° is, however, considerably less than the actual angle of about 90°. Thus if there is to be an intramolecular H-bonding in *o*-nitrothiophenol it cannot be rectilinear. This factor must at least partially be contributing to the non-existence of significant intramolecular H-bonding in *o*-nitrothiophenol.

It is of interest to note that even in the case of an *o*-hydroxysulphone (5) proper geometrical conditions exist for intramolecular H-bonding. It is indeed known that strong chelation exists in *o*-hydroxysulphones²⁶ (S-H...O distance is 2.6 Å and CŜH is 93°).

An examination of structure 6 reveals that if the NO₂ group of *o*-nitrothiophenol is replaced by

CH₃SO₂ group, S-H...O can be made very nearly linear. These considerations led us to believe that the geometry of *o*-methylsulphonylthiophenol (6) is more favourable for intramolecular H-bonding than that of *o*-nitrothiophenol. Hence the spectral behaviour of *o*- and *p*-methylsulphonylthiophenols and their methyl ethers in cyclohexane as well as in ethanol was studied. The observed solvent effect and the effect of methylation are shown in Table 3. Analysing the spectral data as in previous cases, the solvent effect suggests beyond doubt that there is intramolecular H-bonding in *o*-methylsulphonylthiophenol. But the effect of methylation does not indicate that. A case like this must be interpreted as weak H-bonding.

TABLE 3—UV SPECTRA OF *o*- AND *p*-METHYLSULPHONYLTHIOPHENOLS AND THEIR METHYL ETHERS

Compd.	Cyclohexane		Ethanol	
	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$
Solvent effect				
<i>o</i> -HS.C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ Me	296	2400	286	5700
	248	6600	245	4650
<i>p</i> -HS.C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ Me	270	15400	270	15000
Effect of methylation				
<i>o</i> -MeS.C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ Me	301	3000		
	261	9100		
<i>p</i> -MeS.C ₆ H ₄ .SO ₂ Me	274	17700		
	222	8100		

The recognition of a weak H-bond in *o*-chlorophenol²⁷⁻²⁹ prompted us to study the spectral behaviour of *o*- and *p*-chlorothiophenols and their methyl ethers in hexane and ethanol. The data obtained are given in Table 4. In the case of *o*-chlorothiophenol, change of solvent from hexane to ethanol causes a hypsochromic shift of the *B*-band and a bathochromic shift of the *K*-band. Methylation causes a bathochromic shift of the both bands. Taking both effects into consideration it may be said that there is no significant intramolecular H-bonding in *o*-chlorothiophenol, perhaps there is very weak H-bonding⁶.

TABLE 4—UV SPECTRA OF *o*- AND *p*-CHLOROTHIOPHENOLS AND THEIR METHYL ETHERS

Compd.	Hexane		Ethanol	
	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$
<i>o</i> -Chlorothiophenol	283	900	275	3450
	259	8200	243	6800
<i>p</i> -Chlorothiophenol	244	11300	248	10100
<i>o</i> -Chloroethoanisole	287	1540	285	1280
	255	10500	253	10400
<i>p</i> -Chloroethoanisole	261	12100	260	14200

At this stage it appeared necessary to examine the possibility of detecting H-bond in *o*-chlorophenol itself by the uv spectroscopic method. So the necessary spectral data were obtained (Table 5) and analysed. The solvent effect seems to indicate weak intramolecular H-bonding in *o*-chlorophenol

TABLE 5—UV SPECTRA OF *o*- AND *p*-CHLOROPHENOLS AND THEIR METHYL ETHERS

Compd.	Hexane		Ethanol	
	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$\epsilon_{\max}$
<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .OH	281	1850	277	2000
	215	3900	215	5300
<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .OH	282	1800	283	1700
	225	8000	228	8650
<i>o</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .OMe	283	2000		
	223	5900		
<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .OMe	290	1000		
	228	7100		

but the effect of methylation does not indicate it. In view of the fact that infrared spectra²⁷ and dipole moment studies^{28,29} also suggest weak intramolecular H-bonding in this compound, it may be concluded that such weak H-bonding can be detected only by the solvent effect and not by methylation.

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